

I.FAST

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MILESTONE REPORT

VARIABLE Dipole for the Elettra Ring: Prototype acceptance test

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ABSTRACT

The VArIable Dipole for the Elettra Ring (VADER) task, driven by the I.FAST European project (Deliverable 7.3), aimed at developing a prototype of a new full length variable field dipole design magnet which includes a transverse gradient allowing a further reduction of the horizontal emittance in the upgraded ELETTRA storage ring. A prototype of this magnet was designed by the CIEMAT laboratory and fabricated by KYMA company. This note presents and discusses the magnetic measurement serving as acceptance tests of the magnet prototype conducted at ELETTRA.

I.FAST Consortium, 2021

For more information on IFAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1 INTRODUCTION.....4

2 MAGNETIC MEASUREMENTS4

3 CONCLUSION9

Executive summary

The Variable Dipole Elettra Ring (VADER) was specified by CERN for reducing the emittance for the ELETTRA ring up to a factor of two, by using a novel PM concept with a hyperbolic field profile and peak field at the centre reaching 2.3 T. After the magnetic design at CIEMAT, the magnet was fabricated at KYMA and measured at ELETTRA. The measurements show an excellent agreement with the predicted magnetic field in both dipole and quadrupole component and good field quality. This report presents the magnetic measurement set-up and results which served as acceptance tests.

1 Introduction

In the framework of I.FAST WP7 a magnet prototype based on an innovative dipole magnet design with longitudinal varying dipole field, including a transverse gradient has been built (Task 7.3). The magnet concept was already established for the case of the CLIC damping rings, and the study demonstrated the significant reduction of the horizontal emittance. The design has been modified and adapted to the lattice of the upgraded ELETTRA light source storage ring, in order to reduce up to a factor two the horizontal emittance beyond the 140 pm proposed for ELETTRA 2.0 study. The use of such new magnet involves the optics calculations for the storage ring Multi-Bend Achromat cell, by replacing all the dipoles with longitudinally varying ones with an optimised hyperbolic field profile. CIEMAT carried out the magnetic and mechanical design, and the magnet prototype has been manufactured by KYMA, a leading industrial partner in the magnet technologies for X-ray sources and, in particular, insertion devices. Finally the magnet has been measured at ELETTRA and this report presents the magnetic measurement and results which served as acceptance tests.

2 Magnetic measurements

An overview of the final VADER magnetic system is shown in fig. 1 (more details are reported in Deliverable 7.3), the magnet has been realized at Kyma (fig.2) and then moved to ELETTRA Sincrotrone Trieste for magnetic measurements and acceptance testing where has been positioned close to the bench specifically designed (fig.3).

Fig. 1 VADER final design and main characteristics.

Fig. 2 Photo of the assembled VADER magnet in KYMA.

Fig. 3 Picture of the magnetic measurement set-up bench at ELETTRA including the bench and 3D field mapper.

After the phase of mechanical pre-alignment and magnetic alignment, the field produced by the magnet was mapped on the median plane on a rectangular strip measuring $L \times W = 1100 \times 52$ mm. A SENIS 3D Digital Teslameter 3MH4 calibrated from 0 to 7 Tesla was used for the measurement (characteristics reported in Annexe 1).

In order to evaluate the quality of the field in a potentially real case, the trajectory of a single electron at 2.4 GeV was calculated on the mapping as above. The values of the vertical magnetic field B_y , its quadrupole component B_2 and the first three multipole errors (B_3 , B_4 and B_5) were then evaluated on this trajectory in the gradient field region of ± 5 mm. In order to compare as best as possible the design results with the measurements, the same was done on the field mapping obtained in the Opera simulation.

In Fig.4, the plots of the simulation and measurement results are shown, in particular the field mapping together with the field values on the calculated trajectory and the limits of the relative good field region for the dipole component of the magnet.

Fig. 4 Simulated and measured dipole field including the considered good field region (top) and corresponding electron trajectory estimated with two methods (bottom).

Finally fig. 5 shows the main dipole and quadrupole components as measured along the VADER magnet.

As can be seen, there is an excellent correlation between the simulated and measured values, indicating excellent modelling and, at the same time, the construction of the actual magnet. Small asymmetries were observed in the longitudinal distribution of B_y and B_2 which may be linked to very small alignment errors in the assembled parts and/or inhomogeneity of the ferrous parts. A future action would be to carry out accurate tuning of the assembly in order to minimise these differences and, at the same time, obtain a measure of the mechanical sensitivities for this.

Fig. 5 Main dipole and quadrupole components as measured along the VADER magnet.

3 Conclusion

The final magnetic measurements carried out on VADER magnet at ELETTRA show an excellent agreement of the main components with respect to the predicted values by simulations, including a good field quality.

Small deviations with respect to the simulated values will be addressed in a later phase by adjustments of the measurement mole positioning including positioning of the magnet but also mechanical adjustments with which the magnet is equipped for fine field tuning.

The positive acceptance tests will shape the industrialisation procedure towards a series fabrication of such an innovative magnet device and its full inclusion in the upgrades of ELETTRA and of other synchrotron light sources.

4 Annex: Characteristics of SENIS 3MH4 Digital 3D Teslameter

DESCRIPTION:

SENIS 3D Digital Teslameter 3MH4 redefines magnetic field measurement with unmatched precision, stability, and adaptability. With its absolute accuracy of below 0.1% (1'000ppm), it sets the wide standards in magnetic field measurement. Stability is key, and this device maintains rock-solid digital readings, ensuring consistent and reliable measurement data.

Unparalleled spatial resolution at $0.10 \times 0.01 \times 0.10 \text{ mm}^3$ of the 3-axis Hall probe empowers detailed exploration of magnetic fields. Probe interchangeability simplifies switching probes without sacrificing accuracy, while $<100\text{ppm}/^\circ\text{C}$ temperature stability guarantees reliable measurements across various conditions.

With very high magnetic DC resolution better than 1ppm RMS @ $\pm 2 \text{ T}$, up to 4 (four) selectable field ranges ($\pm 0.1 \text{ T}$ to $\pm 20 \text{ T}$), and seamless connectivity through USB2.0 and LAN, it's a versatile tool for diverse applications.

This teslameter is invaluable for mapping magnetic fields, characterizing systems, current sensing, and quality control in laboratories, production lines, and magnet systems. It's the ultimate tool for precision in magnetic field measurement, offering the future of magnetic field analysis.

Figure 1: 3-channel digital teslameter 3MH4: front panel (left); rear panel (right)

KEY FEATURES:

- Digital teslameter with integrated 3-axis Hall Probe (Bx, By, Bz) and temperature sensor.
 - High measurement DC accuracy @ Sampling rate 10 SPS (SPS - samples per second):
 - < 0.1% (1'000 ppm FS) @ ± 0.1 T, ± 0.5 T and ± 2 T ranges, and
 - determined upon a High-Field DC Calibration Table for higher field ranges @ $B > \pm 2$ T.
 - Very good stability of the digital readings.
 - Very high spatial resolution: overall FSV of the applied 3D Hall IC in the probe is only $0.10 \times 0.01 \times 0.10$ mm³.
 - Detachable Hall probes: DC calibration data of each Hall probe are stored in an integrated EEPROM.
 - High temperature stability: $< \pm 100$ ppm/°C (± 0.01 %/°C).
 - 4 (four) selectable magnetic field ranges: ± 0.1 T, ± 0.5 T, ± 2 T, and up to ± 20 T *
 (* the last is in-factory calibrated up to ± 2 T; optionally: calibration up to maximum field ± 9 T).
 - Selectable Sampling rate: (10 - 7'500) SPS.
 - Very high magnetic DC resolution @ Sampling rate 10 SPS: < 1 ppm RMS @ ± 2 T range: $1 \mu\text{T}_{\text{RMS}}$ for perpendicular (By) and $2 \mu\text{T}_{\text{RMS}}$ for planar components (Bx & Bz) of a measured magnetic field.
 - Measurement of DC & AC magnetic fields.
 - Frequency Bandwidth: DC - 2.5 kHz (-3 dB).
 - AC Accuracy: see the Table 1 below.
 - Analog outputs: uncalibrated.
 - 24-bit A/D Convertor.
 - Triggers Internal and external - Single shot, Manual and Continuous.
 - TFT LCD graphic display (108 x 65mm) for Bx, By, Bz, Btot, and the Th (probe) and Te (box) temperatures.
 - Data acquisition & visualization PC Software runs on Windows 11 / 10 / 8 / 7 OS via USB2.0 interface.
- * Ethernet (LAN) interface is under development (expected latest by end of Q2 2025).

Sampling rate [SPS]	10	30	50	60	100	500	1'000	2'000	3'750	7'500
Averaging time [ms]	100	33.333	20	16.667	10	2	1	0.5	0.267	0.133
Resolution [μT_{RMS}]	0.8	0.9	1	1.1	1.2	2	2.5	3	4	5
f(-10 ppm) [Hz]	0.03	0.08	0.13	0.15	0.27	1.4	2.6	5	9	10
f(-100 ppm) [Hz]	0.08	0.24	0.39	0.47	0.8	4	8	18	25	30
f(-0.1%) [Hz]	0.25	0.74	1.23	1.48	2.5	12.5	24	50	75	90
f(-1%) [Hz]	0.78	2.34	3.9	4.69	7.8	39	77	155	230	300
f _c (-3 dB) [Hz]	4.4	13.3	22.2	26.5	44	220	434	880	1340	2500

Table 1: The table shows the combinations of the magnetic signal frequencies, measurement resolutions and bandwidths that are achievable with the 3MH4 teslameter. Displayed values apply to each measurement axis Bx, By & Bz.